

Speculation on Consequences of an Exact Energy, but Imprecise Time on a Quantum Bound State

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Ideas of conservation of energy and momentum hold both in classical mechanics and in quantum mechanics, which may make it confusing that a bound state may be written in terms of free particle states $\exp(ipx)$ with the possibility $pp/2m > E$ (energy) of the bound state. One might suggest then that E is an average energy because one averages over various $\exp(ipx)$ states, but E is binding energy, and this should be a precise value, like rest mass. We suggest that $\exp(-E1 t) \exp(ipx)$ where $E1=pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic case) means that one does measure p at a precise x or $E1$ or E at a precise t (time). Thus, there seems to be no violation of conservation of energy to have $pp/2m > E$ because $pp/2m$ exists at an unknown time as well as E and so in a sense there is no violation of conservation of energy unless $pp/2m > E$ persists for times over \hbar/E . To violate conservation of energy, one would have to show that either at a precise instant t it is violated and this cannot be done given $dt=\hbar/E$, $dt1=\hbar/E1$ otherwise showing that it is conserved on average seems to be good enough, which is what it is done with quantum bound states. This feature is important because one cannot have a given p (with $\exp(ipx)$) at a precise x , so one needs to create an average kinetic energy at an exact x using $\exp(ipx)s$ to link with $V(x)$. This gives the sense of an average E , but this may be considered to be a precise value over a resolution of $dt=\hbar/E$ and not precise t points.

Conservation of Energy and Momentum

Conservation of energy and momentum are ideas introduced in Newtonian mechanics which are carried over into quantum mechanics as Newtonian mechanics was developed first. In Newtonian mechanics, however, one knows sharp positions x and times t and so one may say that one has $pp/2m$ at x at t or $V(x)$ at a precise x,t , where $V(x)$ is a potential. In Newtonian mechanics it seems that conservation of energy and momentum is associated with sharp x , t values.

If one wishes to have the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + (px)x + (py)y + (pz)z$ have each term equal to 1 because they are completely independent in terms of measurement, then:

$$dt= \hbar/E, \quad dx=\hbar/(px), \quad dy= \hbar/(py), \quad dz= \hbar/(pz) \quad ((1))$$

This means that neither dt or dx is sharp. Even though energy may be conserved, at what time is it conserved? One cannot pinpoint the time and so it must be conserved at least over the time interval \hbar/E . The same considerations hold for momentum (px) and dx . We argue that this may be an important issue for quantum bound states.

In classical mechanics, one has $V(x)$ which is fine because one has a precise x value linked to a precise t , but in quantum mechanics there is no precise x value or t value. Thus, $V(x)$ is a kind of average at x it seems. Thus, we suggest that in the quantum case one must view dynamics differently.

Quantum Bound State

In classical mechanics:

$$E = \text{Kinetic energy} + V(x) \quad ((1))$$

As noted, there is no precise t or x in quantum mechanics (as shown and so one may only be interpreted as a kind of average statement. This at first seems like a problem because one does not want an average E as it may represent binding energy. Binding energy, like rest mass, is precise. For a single particle, it is not the case that there exists a heat bath, like in the case of an ideal gas, which would allow it to obtain a very large amount of energy even though one averages its kinetic energy is $3/2 kT$ (T =temperature, 3-dimensions).

Thus, the notion of average energy is a problem, but given that one does not have precise x , t resolution, one can only have the notion of energy in an interval \hbar/E and the notion of dx in intervals of $\hbar/(px)$ for various (px) values. As a result, if one were to say that a bound state has an energy of E , but that a single particle could have a nonrelativistic kinetic energy of $(px)(px)/2m$, neither have meaning at an instant t and so one cannot say that energy is not conserved at an instant t if $(px)(px)/2m > E$. Only if $(px)(px)/2m$ persists for times over \hbar/E can one argue that E is not the bound energy, we argue. This then leads to a very different scenario from classical physics in which $pp/2m \leq E$.

In classical physics, one measures the momentum of a particle at a precise x, t . Even though the particle is continually accelerating, p is a leading order value and gives the sense of free motion. In quantum mechanics, if one wishes to have the sense of a precise p as a leading order term, then there is a $dx = \hbar/(px)$ uncertainty region which means that $V(x)$ varies within this region. $V(x)$, however, must be seen as an average, it seems, because there is no sense of a precise x point for a quantum particle.

A second issue which arises is that if one accepts $V(x)$ and calls it an average, then one requires an average Kinetic Energy at precise x as well to have $((1))$ satisfied. This leads to a problem if one tries to use a leading precise (px) value as in classical mechanics as this can never be linked to a precise x . To have a KE average, we argue that one has no choice but to include various precise (px) values, even ones for which $(px)(px)/2m > E$. As we have noted, this does not violate conservation of energy.

As a result, using $\exp(ipx)$ for each $(px)=p$, which shows the $dx = \hbar/(p)$ restriction, one may find average kinetic energy using:

$$KE_{ave} = -1/2m \left\{ \sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} \quad ((2))$$

In other words, one is forced to adopt an entangled picture of many p values which create an average KE at a precise x point. It is only in an entangled state or averaged state in which a precise x point has a meaning in the same sense that $V(x)$ does.

One may rephrase this noting that a precise free particle p gives rise to uncertainty in x , so one needs an average (entanglement) of various free p 's to obtain the notion of an average (e.g. KE) at a precise x . This average KE added to $V(x)$ yields a constant E , which seems like an average, but if one remembers that $dt = \hbar/E$, then there is a time interval associated with each

E measurement and so this seems to be consistent with an averaging process of $\exp(ipx)$ s. If dt were 0, this would not be possible it seems, because any $pp/2m$ would exist at an instant, while E would exist at the same instant.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum free particle time and spatial uncertainties, $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$, linked with $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ where $E = p^2/2m$, have large consequences on a quantum bound state. Even though the notions of conservation of energy and momentum still hold for quantum mechanics (free as well as bound particles), as in classical mechanics, dt and dx means that there is no notion of a precise t or x and one cannot say, as in classical mechanics, that E is violated at a precise time. This seems to imply that one may use an average to create E including some p values such that: $pp/2m > E$.

In classical mechanics, this is not possible, we argue, because energy conservation holds at a precise time. In quantum mechanics there is no precise time for the energy and so there is no violation of conservation of energy unless $pp/2m > E$ persists for more than \hbar/E time. This means that one may use averages of free particle $\exp(ipx)$ s to calculate an average kinetic energy at a precise x because there is no notion of a precise x for any $\exp(ipx)$ by itself. It is only through an average that it is possible. Even though this seems to create an average E, when E should be precise because it represents binding energy, the fact that one does not measure E at a precise time means that E can still be considered a precise value even though it is calculated using an average of all $\exp(ipx)$ values, some of which have $pp/2m > E$.